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Engineer to Manager Work-Role Transition: A Single Case Narrative

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ABSTRACT

Promoting engineering talent to managerial and leadership roles has been an on-going challenge for many organizations. A growing body of research suggests that engineers are often ill-prepared for taking up managerial roles, leading to reduced job effectiveness and performance. Moreover, there is a lack of clear understanding of the nature of the engineer to engineering manager transition. To address this gap, this study aims to uncover the lived experiences of recently transitioned engineering managers. More specifically, this paper addresses the following primary research question guiding the study: What are the work-role transition experiences of recently transitioned engineering managers? The data for the larger study comes from interviews with 18 recently transitioned engineering managers. An interpretive qualitative analysis approach is employed to analyse the interview data. To keep the scope of the current account more manageable, this paper presents preliminary results in the form of a holistic narrative for a single participant. By providing rich accounts of one participant's experiences and transition journey, we highlight three major themes emerging from our preliminary findings: 1) psychological and cognitive changes associated with the work-role transition, 2) on-the-job learning and mentoring supports for transition, and 3) social skills as essential attributes for the transition. We conclude with some potential implications for continuing education and professional development programs aimed at engineering professionals. It is expected that this paper will help students, engineering educators, engineering leadership faculty, and industry affiliates reflect on the realities of engineering managerial practices.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Changing organizational structures and job expectations demand that many engineers and other technical professionals transition into managerial and leadership roles very early in their careers [1,2]. Yet engineers and employers alike often characterize this as a difficult transition, leading to a less productive and effective technical, managerial workforce. This, in part, could be attributed to the lack of preparedness of engineers to cope with managerial work demands. Recent studies have also confirmed that engineers are often ill-prepared to meet the responsibilities of managerial roles [2,3] such as effectively delegating work, moving away from technical work tasks, etc. Many also struggle with a lack of understanding of what managerial roles entail. Some of these challenges have additionally been evident in the lead author's experiences working as an intern at a major telecommunications company. Yet despite a small but growing body of evidence about the criticality of the engineer-to-manager transition and the associated challenges, high-quality empirical research studying various aspects of this transition remains scant.

These observed gaps and challenges serve to ground and motivate further investigation of several issues, including: a) the lack of preparedness of engineers to take up engineering managerial roles; b) the specific challenges engineers face as they move up the ladder as managers; c) the lack of clear understanding of how engineers are promoted to managerial roles; and e) the lack of clarity on training and onboarding processes for new managers. This paper reports preliminary results from a larger qualitative study involving interviews with 18 recently transitioned engineering managers. Here we present preliminary results in the form of a holistic narrative for a single participant. We conclude with some potential implications for continuing education and professional development programs aimed at engineering professionals. It is expected that this paper will help students, engineering educators, engineering leadership faculty, and industry affiliates reflect on the realities of engineering managerial practices.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Career Transition

Historically, career transition has been associated with role change or a change in orientation to existing roles [4]. Recent definitions broaden the scope further by defining the transition as a process of engagement and disengagement from any work role and/or work situation [5]. While authors and scholars have explored a wide range of topics under the broader career transition phenomena from a variety of perspectives, in this study we specifically explore and characterize transition as a change from a technical professional or engineer role to a managerial role.

2.2 Engineer to Manager Transition

While there have been numerous studies to date in nursing, social psychology, management, and other fields focusing on work-role transitions, research specifically focused on the transition from an engineering role to a managerial role remains

scant. Furthermore, in a prior literature review conducted and presented by the authors [6], we discuss how published work on the engineer to manager transition has been mostly limited to three main considerations, namely: 1) competencies and skills required for engineers to transition into managerial roles (e.g. [7,8]); 2) challenges associated with the transition (e.g. [2,3]); and 3) strategies for effective transition (e.g. [9]). We further note that there remains a dearth of literature describing holistic experiences of recently transitioned engineering managers which in turn could uncover several aspects of the transition from the perspective of the engineers themselves [6].

2.3 Work Role Transition Theoretical Framework

For this study on the engineer to manager transition, theoretical concepts from work-role transition models are used as a guiding framework. This framework is well suited for this study, as it revolves around understanding the transition from the individuals' perspectives. The literature on work-role transition is often concerned with addressing questions such as how individuals disengage from one role and engage with a new work role. As synthesized by Anderson [10], work-role transition theories and models explore “aspects of entry into the role, the transference of role expectations, and exit from the previous role” (p. 204) related to any transition.

Work-role transition theory was first proposed by Nicholson [11], who explored aspects of the individuals' adjustment to new roles during transitions. He proposed that individuals in role transitions often go through two types of adjustment processes – role development and personal development. These processes are further accompanied by several changes in individuals' behaviours, identity, formal and informal relationships, etc. Building on Nicholson's model, further studies in the field have also examined the changes associated with the transition for individuals disengaging from old roles and engaging in new roles. In synthesizing the several aspects of changes that are critical to work-role transition, Ashforth and Saks [12] suggest that “work-role transitions often entail a reorientation of goals, attitudes, identity, behavioural routines, informal networks and many other large and small changes” (p. 157). Not surprisingly, most literature on work-role transition addresses one or more aspects of these changes related to the transition experience.

Notably, authors have been approaching the studies on transitions and associated changes from three broad perspectives: psychological, relational (social aspects), and cognitive [10]. The psychological perspective deals with understanding changes and/or adjustments in individuals' physiological constructs such as identity, persona, etc. as individuals transition into new work roles. Similarly, relational changes are often described in terms of individuals' social connections, including inter-personal relationships, informal networks, etc., that are critical for adjustment into a new role. While social and psychological changes are often central to most literature on work-role transition theories and models, Anderson [10] also advocates for exploring the

cognitive or thinking changes associated with the role transition to provide a more holistic understanding of transition.

Although the work-role transition theoretical framework has been used to study nuances of a wide range of role transitions such as from expert clinician to novice academic educator (e.g., Anderson [10]), and from middle manager to senior manager (e.g., Nicholson and West [13]), it has not been used to study the transition process from individual contributor role to engineering managerial role.

3. STUDY DESIGN

The overarching purpose of the larger research project is to explore and understand the meaning making and lived experiences of engineers who have transitioned to engineering managerial roles. In order to describe the transition journeys of engineers as they move into engineering managerial roles, the following primary research question and associated sub-questions are addressed:

Research Question 1 (RQ1): How do engineers describe and make sense of their experiences of transition from individual contributor roles to engineering managerial roles?

- a) How do engineers experience and describe the changes and challenges associated with the transition from individual contributor roles to managerial roles?
- b) How do engineers describe their preparations for the transition?

To address the primary goal of understanding the experiences of recently transitioned engineering managers, we have employed an interpretive qualitative study design. An interpretive approach is concerned with “understand[ing] how people make sense of their lives” (p. 38 [14]), which is central to the research objective for this study. In accordance with this methodology, semi-structured interviews were conducted with 18 recently transitioned engineering managers. Each interview was approximately 60-90 minutes in duration. The data collection phase is mainly inspired by narrative [15] and critical incident [16] interviewing techniques. These methods are employed to elicit grand narratives or stories of the participants’ experiences, which are used for further analysis to address the research questions presented above. The data collection was carried out under appropriate guidelines and approvals for human subjects research.

For the data analysis process, we initially analysed the data using only an inductive thematic analysis approach. However, as we began coding, we realized that the complexity of the transition process would not fully be captured only through the codes. We felt that categorizing data into smaller units did not adequately justify the incredible journeys of transition that the individuals shared with us, as they talked about their experiences moving from engineer to engineering managerial roles. We

thus decided to follow a thematic narrative approach inspired by Kellam, Gerow & Walther [17] for each participant to describe their journeys of transition.

The following steps were followed to construct these third-person narratives. First, we identified critical incidents from the interview data that are relevant to the research objective – experiences of engineers as they transition to managerial roles. Second, we chronologically arrange the incidents. Third, we identify quotes from each interview transcript that validates the narrative plot. Finally, we will include our analysis as we develop the thematic analysis narratives that are interjected with our interpretations of each participant's experiences and journeys. Once the narratives are developed, we will also identify specific themes/patterns emerging from the narratives and interview transcripts as relevant to the research questions.

To keep the scope of the paper manageable, here we present a single participant narrative highlighting our analysis of the major themes running through the transcript. Two interviews, including initial and follow-up interviews conducted with a single participant, are used to construct the narrative using the steps mentioned above. The narrative begins with a brief profile of the participant and then presents a series of incidents that are thematically related to the research questions.

4. FINDINGS

After receiving a master's degree in Construction Management from a large research university in the Southwest U.S., Kris took a position as a technical analyst at Pie Corporation (all identifying information anonymized) in the Midwestern U.S. Over a period of about 6 years, Kris moved up the ranks in the company, from a technical analyst (or consultant) role to a program manager. In his current role as a program manager, Kris's responsibilities not only include managing a portfolio of projects but also managing and leading seven employees who directly report to him. In talking about his responsibilities as a program manager, Kris also emphasizes the people aspect of his role when he states: "So, my current responsibilities also include managing the people as a mentor, so I'll be, I'm not just a project, I'm also a people manager where I manage and mentor the constituents that report to me."

Transitioning from an individual contributor role to a program manager has been a "big change" for Kris. Reflecting on this journey, Kris not surprisingly characterizes the transition as big and difficult as he talks about the associated increases in stakes and responsibilities. Throughout the interview, he uses the words "challenging," "big," and "difficult" to describe the transition. For example, as Kris explains:

So it's been a big transition from being an individual contributor to a people manager as well as now the stakes have increased. As a consultant, I could always go back to my manager to manage them. But right now, I have to manage escalations. So that was a big challenging transition that I had to make for myself.

This experience of difficulty in navigating transition aligns well with prior empirical research on the engineer to manager transition [3] as well as the work-role transition theory [6]. Primarily, as Kris began to enter his new role, he experienced several changes that he wasn't quite prepared for. These, in turn, made the transition difficult for him. One such change that Kris had to cope with was the initial perceptions he had about the managerial role. Contrary to his expectations, the managerial role demanded more work from him than he had perceived:

Yeah. So when I was a consultant, I used to think: what is the job of a manager, what does he do? He doesn't do anything; he's always free. He just assigns activities and then- (laughter). Once I've moved into this role, I really understood the pain and the amount of responsibility of a project manager. It's not just tracking the project to the schedule or budget, it's a lot more about soft skills and how do you handle your customer escalations and also how do you make sure your resources are also, it's about selling something to the associates, not just assigning work to them. So you need to make sure we get the required interest from the customer to do the activities, not just assigning the activity to them. Now I understand how much work it is and how much struggle or pain the managers go through.

One of the other changes that Kris struggled with was the addition of the people management component in his new role. Not having any prior formal experience managing people, Kris struggled a bit initially with this new job responsibility. He realized that he was now “accountable for the whole team” and not just for himself, which was something he had to learn on the job.

While aspects of the transition were challenging, Kris adapted to some changes associated with the new role rather confidently. Positive experiences also helped him ease into the new role more quickly. For instance, although Kris had to assimilate himself into the new role as a manager, he still retained his former identity as a technical contributor:

I identify myself as a project manager right now, but I cannot forget what I have gone through as a [technical] consultant, so I still know the reality of that role, so I don't, um, push my people because I know what they are going through. So instead, I try to understand their problem and come up with a solution, so it's easier for them to handle that too.

Despite the challenges thrown at him due to the role change, Kris eventually found ways of navigating these challenges as he spent more time in his new job role. Interestingly, Kris had a steep learning curve in his first six months of transition. In talking about his preparations and learning to assimilate into the new role, Kris states that he learned most of it “on the job.” Notably, the mentoring he received on the job

from his managers as well as the initial job shadowing of his manager greatly helped him cope with the transition. Referencing the mentoring relationship he had formed in his initial years, Kris says,

I was assigned a mentor from the senior leadership team who helped me with project management aspects. He also guided me if I went off track on something. There wasn't any formal classroom teaching, but it was mostly on-the-job learning.

After spending close to two years in his new role, Kris finally feels settled and confident to handle the job responsibilities of a manager. In this narrative, we also see a shift in Kris's perspective in dealing with the role change. Whereas initially he was mostly focused on trying to stay afloat and navigating through the challenges, now his attention has shifted toward playing on his strengths and weaknesses to excel and succeed in the role:

So, I think I have improved in my communication skills, so soft skills, but I'm not yet, I think I'm not yet perfect in it, but I have improved a lot since I've started. Also, I'm good at now understanding the expectations of all the different people that are involved. And also learning to be a better program and people manager than just a manager.

In this quote, Kris characterizes his transition as a positive learning experience. This is quite contrary to his initial experiences of feeling the role was difficult and challenging. Now he is in a state where he is looking to learn more and grow further in his role.

5. SUMMARY, DISCUSSION, AND IMPLICATIONS

Kris's account of his transition journey provides a brief yet critical window into the world of engineering managerial work practices. While the narrative provides a holistic view of the transition as experienced by the participant, we also intend to shed light on three major themes emerging from the narrative transition including the psychological and cognitive changes, preparations for the transition including on the job learning and mentorship, and the emphasis of social skills required to successfully transition into the new role.

In terms of changes experienced, the subject alludes to changes in psychological and cognitive constructs as prescribed by the work-role transition framework [10]. For instance, psychological shifts are evident as Kris references shifts in his identity as he talks about considering himself a manager along with retaining his old self-identity as a technical professional. Similarly, in terms of cognitive shifts, Kris talks extensively about the disconnect between managerial role expectations and reality. Primarily, he was surprised by the amount and kind of work the new role entails, which was quite inconsistent with his earlier perceptions of a managerial role.

However, differing from prior research on the work-role transition framework, we observe that Kris does not mention any substantial relational changes.

In describing the preparations for the transition, not surprisingly, Kris credits on-the-job learning as his primary source for learning about and preparing for the new role. Through his narrative, it is evident that having a mentor also bolstered his learning and preparations for entering the new role. These insights into learning mechanisms suggest the importance of mentorship programs in organizations to enhance the transition process for engineers. A robust job-shadowing process could also help engineers transition more quickly and productively into managerial roles.

Through Kris's narrative, we also find that social skills are essential for successfully transitioning from technical into managerial roles. Reflecting on his new-found appreciation for communication and social skills, Kris states that he has improved a lot in this area, which helped ease his transition into the managerial role. Perhaps not surprisingly, elsewhere in the transcript Kris also advises new engineers to work on their social skills to grow in their careers if they wish to move into managerial or leadership roles. This emphasis on social skills reflects the complex socio-technical nature of engineering managerial work practices.

The next phase of this research study centers on developing similar narratives for the remaining 17 participants, which will in turn allow us to identify emerging patterns across the narratives as well to provide a more holistic view of the transition. Through the thematic narratives and findings resulting from this paper and the larger project, we hope to showcase the realities of engineering management practice. We believe the study can benefit several stakeholders. First, the findings contribute to a growing body of research on engineering practice in workplace settings. Second, the study will likely be of interest to recent graduates and early career engineers looking to advance in their careers. More specifically, the narratives on the lived experiences of recently transitioned managers might serve as a valuable guiding resource for future engineering managers. Third, the findings will benefit Human Resource (HR) staff and other industry leaders looking to understand better ways of developing engineering talent in companies. Fourth, the findings will benefit engineering educators and faculty of engineering leadership development programs by providing them insights about the nature of engineering managerial work practices which can, in turn, inform better ways of preparing future engineering managers and leaders.

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